

Raw data of Figure 2

Fingolimod and Fingolimod-Phosphate (Fingolimod-P) plasma levels for each patient/sample

ID analysis	Time of blood sampling	Fingolimod concentration (ng/mL)	Fingolimod-P concentration (ng/mL)	Fingolimod-P-to-Fingolimod ratio
Sample-1	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-2	T6	0.328	1.070	3.262
Sample-3	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-4	T6	0.448	1.230	2.746
Sample-5	T12	0.901	1.740	1.931
Sample-6	T24	0.937	1.640	1.750
Sample-7	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-8	T6	0.822	1.250	1.521
Sample-9	T12	0.412	0.954	2.316
Sample-10	T24	0.421	1.040	2.470
Sample-11	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-12	T6	0.535	1.040	1.944
Sample-13	T12	0.369	1.350	3.659
Sample-14	T24	0.580	1.440	2.483
Sample-15	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-16	T6	0.719	1.560	2.170
Sample-17	T12	0.295	0.653	2.214
Sample-18	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-19	T6	0.977	1.460	1.494
Sample-20	T12	0.353	1.030	2.918
Sample-21	T24	0.984	1.340	1.362
Sample-22	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-23	T6	0.316	0.521	1.649
Sample-24	T12	0.347	0.559	1.611
Sample-25	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-26	T6	0.174	0.641	3.684

Sample-27	T12	0.091	0.747	8.209
Sample-28	T24	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-29	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-30	T6	0.543	1.220	2.247
Sample-31	T12	0.422	0.728	1.725
Sample-32	T24	0.952	1.950	2.048
Sample-33	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-34	T6	0.914	1.090	1.193
Sample-35	T12	0.713	1.220	1.711
Sample-36	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-37	T6	0.327	1.390	4.251
Sample-38	T12	0.461	1.400	3.037
Sample-39	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-40	T6	0.959	1.470	1.533
Sample-41	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-42	T6	0.048	0.249	5.188
Sample-43	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-44	T6	0.588	1.560	2.653
Sample-45	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-
Sample-46	T6	0.533	1.410	2.645
Sample-47	T12	0.336	0.962	2.863
Sample-48	T0	BLQ	BLQ	-

BLQ: below limit of quantification

Mean, SD, median and Q1-Q3 calculation from GraphPad Prism 7.05

Parameters: Column statistics

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Descriptive Statistics

☒ Minimum and maximum	☒ Mean, SD, SEM	☐ Skewness and kurtosis
☒ Quartiles (Median, 25th and 75th percentile)	☐ Coefficient of variation	☐ Column sum
☐ Percentile <input type="text" value="90"/>	☐ Geometric mean	

Confidence intervals

☒ CI of the mean	☐ CI of geometric mean	☒ CI of median
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Confidence level:

Test if the values come from a Gaussian distribution

☐ D'Agostino-Pearson omnibus normality test (recommended)
☐ Shapiro-Wilk normality test
☐ Kolmogorov-Smirnov test with Dallal-Wilkinson-Lilliefors P value (not recommended)

Inferences

☐ One-sample t test. Are column means significantly different than a hypothetical value?	Hypothetical value <input type="text" value="0"/>
☐ Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Compare column medians to a hypothetical value.	(often 0.0, 1.0 or 100)

When a value equals the hypothetical value:

Subcolumns

☒ Compute the mean of the subcolumns for each row, and then calculate the column statistic for each column
☐ Compute column statistics for each subcolumn separately

Output

P value style:

Show: significant digits.

Make these choices be the default for future analyses.

Fingolimod

GraphPad Prism 7.05 - [New_raw_data.pzfx:Col. stats of FTY720_median_Q1-Q3]

File Edit View Insert Change Arrange Family Window Help

Prism File Sheet Undo Clipboard Analysis Interpret Change Draw Write

Col. stats		A	B	C
		T=6	T=12	T=24
		Y	Y	Y
1	Number of values	15	11	6
2				
3	Minimum	0.141	0.176	0
4	25% Percentile	0.316	0.306	0.3908
5	Median	0.547	0.4	0.7195
6	75% Percentile	0.722	0.511	1.031
7	Maximum	0.888	0.803	1.17
8				
9	Mean	0.5337	0.4388	0.6857
10	Std. Deviation	0.224	0.1795	0.4186
11	Std. Error of Mean	0.05785	0.05412	0.1709
12				

Fingolimod-P

GraphPad Prism 7.05 - [New_raw_data.pzfx:Col. stats of FTY720-P_median_Q1-Q3]

File Edit View Insert Change Arrange Family Window Help

Prism File Sheet Undo Clipboard Analysis Interpret Change

Col. stats		A	B	C
		T=6	T=12	T=24
		Y	Y	Y
1	Number of values	15	11	6
2				
3	Minimum	0.25	0.56	0
4	25% Percentile	1.04	0.73	0.78
5	Median	1.23	0.96	1.39
6	75% Percentile	1.46	1.35	1.718
7	Maximum	1.56	1.74	1.95
8				
9	Mean	1.144	1.031	1.235
10	Std. Deviation	0.3937	0.3639	0.677
11	Std. Error of Mean	0.1016	0.1097	0.2764
12				

Fingolimod-P-to-Fingolimod ratio

GraphPad Prism 7.05 - [New_raw_data.pzfx:Col. stats of FTY720P-to-FTY720_ratio_median_Q1-Q3]

File Edit View Insert Change Arrange Family Window Help

Col. stats		A	B	C
		T=6	T=12	T=24
		Y	Y	Y
1	Number of values	15	11	5
2				
3	Minimum	1.281	1.611	1.362
4	25% Percentile	1.694	1.778	1.382
5	Median	2.161	2.385	1.996
6	75% Percentile	2.627	2.917	2.398
7	Maximum	3.767	4.244	2.585
8				
9	Mean	2.271	2.501	1.911
10	Std. Deviation	0.7017	0.7912	0.5273
11	Std. Error of Mean	0.1812	0.2386	0.2358
12				